

FAULTS AND PROMINENT LINEAMENTS: MIGRATORY ROUTES OF WATER FROM LAKE CHAD TO THE BENUE TROUGH

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ABSTRACT

Comprehensive studies of groundwater resources in Lake Chad region have been embarked upon by several workers. The contribution of faults and other prominent lineaments to the dwindling resources of Lake Chad water and its movement are vital issues that must be addressed. Based on recent land satellite and shuttle images, prominent lineaments trending NE-SW were delineated. Five controlled source audio-frequency magnetotelluric profiles made, perpendicular to the general trend of the observed lineament, revealed deep seated faults with similar orientation. This clearly suggests that the said faults might be potential migratory routes of water from Lake Chad to the Benue Trough.

KEYWORDS: Lake Chad, Lineaments, Routes, Migratory, Satellite Images, Benue Trough.

INTRODUCTION

Lake Chad, an extensive inland Lake with a large body of fresh water in this Sahel region, is considered a vital source of potable water by dwellers of that region. However, the shortage of potable water in this region is often aggravated by drought and desertification.

According to Isiorho (1989), Lake Chad has on occasions completely or almost completely dried up, as evident from prehistoric sand dunes found on the Lake bottom. Located in a semi-arid region with a low annual rainfall of 30mm and a high evaporation rate of 2mm/year (Rouche, 1980; Carmouze, 1983) coupled with its proximity to the Sahara desert, the southern part of Lake Chad shrinks during periods of low annual rainfall. Lake Chad is not only the main source of water in the region, it also recharges the underlying aquifers through seepage from the lake bed (Isiorho and Matisoff, 1990).

Several workers (Cratchley, 1960; Cratchley *et al*, 1984) have mapped structural features around Lake Chad. Durand (1982) observed that many of the structures around Lake Chad, covered by thick sediments of the Quaternary Chad Formation, may be visible at the surface.

Observations of Land satellite and shuttle images made by Isiorho *et al* (1991) in the south west portion of the Lake Chad Basin revealed the presence of linear features. A further study of the area by Isiorho and Nkereuwem (1996) resulted in the delineation of several prominent lineaments the least of which was twenty kilometers long.

RESISTIVITY PROFILING

The existence of at least one of the said prominent lineaments observed from the land satellite and shuttle images was later confirmed by geophysics. A 14km long N-S resistivity profiling perpendicular to the said prominent lineament was conducted across it (the profile is shown as a broken line in fig 1). The Wenner configuration was adopted with a 30m electrode separation. Both the terrameter SAS 300C and the strata scout resistivity meter were used for data acquisition.

A segment of the resistivity profile (about 3km long and lying between the 9th and 12km of the said 14km long profile), with lowest resistivity values was observed to correspond to the inferred lineament (fig 2).

The prominent lineament was suggested in that work to be a basement fracture.

TDS

Several water samples were collected within the study area. The depth of sampling varied from 0.6 to 1.6m. It was observed that total dissolved solids (TDS) in the groundwater tended to increase with distance from the Lake. It was further observed that TDS values were generally low in the vicinity of the inferred lineament (fig 1, labelled Z), suggesting that the lineament is indeed a fracture which acts as a Local recharge zone. This is because groundwater recharge by direct rainwater through the fracture zone would have lower TDS values because of the short distance travelled by the said groundwater, relative to groundwater in the surrounding areas (Isiorho and Nkereuwem 1996).

THE PRESENT STUDY

This work seeks to utilize the CSAMT method to establish whether or not there is a relationship between inferred lineaments established by Isiorho and Nkereuwem (1996), the Benue Trough and the diminishing size of the lake water.

Fig. 1. Map showing the prominent lineaments visible on all the Landsat images, the resistivity profile (indicated as a broken line), and the TDS values of some groundwater and lake water samples (After Isiorho & Nkereuwem, 1996.)

CONTROLLED SOURCE AUDIO-FREQUENCY MAGNETOTELLURICS (CSAMT)

The CSAMT method is a frequency-domain electromagnetic technique which utilizes a fixed grounded dipole as an artificial signal source. This technique is similar to the natural-source magnetotellurics (MT) and audio frequency magnetotellurics (AMT) techniques; the main differences centre around the use of the artificial CSAMT signal source at a finite distance. The source provides a stable, dependable and repeatable signal resulting in higher precision and economical measurements than are usually obtainable with natural source measurements in the same spectral bands (Zonge and Hughes, 1993).

Since its introduction in the mid-1970s, CSAMT has been used in exploration for petroleum, geothermal resources, massive sulfides, base and precious metals, structures, lithologies and sources of groundwater contamination. The CSAMT is a relatively new geophysical technique. Not much is known about CSAMT interpretational skills and case histories as such are still being held as proprietary by CSAMT contractors and exploration companies. Apart from the CSAMT work done by the author for FES (NAPIMS) in Magumeri and Ladi Bida sectors of the Chad Basin, no similar work has been reported in Nigeria so far. This paper is in part an attempt to highlight the technical capabilities of the CSAMT method and to encourage its usage as it possesses positive implications in structural delineation as well as petroleum, solid mineral, geothermal and groundwater prospecting.

Fig. 2. Resistivity profile along the New Marte-Kirenowa road. The lowest resistivity readings correspond to the lineament (fracture zone) position (After Isiorho & Nkereuwem, 1996.)

INSTRUMENTATION

The equipment used in the execution of the scalar (2-D) CSAMT survey in the South-western part of Lake Chad were made up of the Turbo Universal V4 console, magnetic sensor coil, porous pots, cables and peripherals, on the receiver line (Rx).

On the transmission line (Tx), we had the MG-3 generator which generated the current signal used in the survey, an IPT-1 transmitter console which introduced the current into the ground, cables and two sets of grounded bipoles (fig. 3a).

The CSAMT method measures electric field (E-field) and magnetic field (H-field) induced by electromagnetic field transmitted from electrical current through grounded bipoles. The CSAMT measurements with V4 receiver can be achieved at a maximum of 34 frequencies ranging from 8192Hz to 0.25Hz producing sounding from the ground surface to several kilometers deep. Any combination of E-field and H-field from the 8 channels, for an example 6 Ex's Hy and Hz, can be simultaneously measured to perform multi-soundings, thus maintaining a high survey production.

The electric field (E-field) which is parallel to the receiver line and the orthogonal magnetic field (H-field) are measured at a specified frequency. The magnitudes of the E-field, the H-field, relative phases, apparent resistivity and phase difference are calculated using the following Cagniard equation.

$$\rho_a = 1/5f (E/H)^2, \phi = \phi_E - \phi_H \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where ρ_a is apparent resistivity in ohm-m; f is frequency in Hz; E is the E-field magnitude in mv/km; H is field magnitude perpendicular to the E-dipole in gammas; ϕ is phase differences in radians; ϕ_E and ϕ_H are E-field and H-field phases respectively.

Field Strength

At a given receiver location, the field strength depends upon various factors: locations of measuring point (relative to transmission bipole), earth resistivity, and measuring frequency. For optimum survey results, it is important to know the approximate expected field strength in order to plan the transmitter location properly.

Apparent Resistivity

The apparent resistivity is calculated from the ratio of orthogonal electric and magnetic fields using the well known Cagniard equation (1) for Magnetotelluric method (MT). It should be noted that this equation is valid in the plane wave region of the electromagnetic field; that is, when the distance between transmitter signal source (Tx) and receiving location (Rx) is sufficiently large. The effective survey area, trapezoidal in shape, indicated in (Fig. 3a) is thus optimised by the maximum possible field strength and by avoiding areas that are too close to the transmitter bipoles.

Far-Field and Near Field

In a CSAMT survey, the distance between the transmitter and receiver locations is constrained, in general, by the requirement that the magnetic and electrical fields be strong enough to permit useful measurements. The paradox is that where the “plane-wave” assumption is valid, the signal may be weak; and where the signal is strongest (near the transmitter), the “plane wave” assumption is no longer true (Yamashita *et al*, 1985).

Fig. 3. Illustration of the CSAMT survey configuration and grid (a) and equipment layout (b).

At some distance from the transmitter bipoles, where the transmitted electromagnetic field becomes a “plane-wave”, it is called “far-field”. (The region between 4-8km in fig 3a). Cagniard equation is valid in the “far-field” to calculate the apparent resistivity. The “far-field” distance, L_f , is given approximately by the following equation:

$$L_f > 3 \text{ skin depth} = 1509 \sqrt{\rho_a/f} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where L_f is in m, ρ_a is resistivity of the homogeneous earth in ohm-m and f is frequency in Hz. This L_f estimate is much more complicated in general field cases where the earth is not homogeneous.

If the distance between transmitter and receiver is much less than L_f , the transmitted field is not “plane-wave” in character. It is referred to as the “near field” (region between 2-4km in fig 3a) and the Cagniard equation over estimates the actual resistivity.

CSAMT Field Work in Dikwa

The site map (fig 4) displays the CSAMT profiles spaced 2km apart and survey configurations used in Dikwa area. The distance between the transmission bipoles varied from 100m during CSAMT calibrations to 1400m during actual survey in Dikwa code-named “TEST 2008”. Three aluminium foil electrodes were grounded at both ends of

the transmission line. Currents ranging from 3.8 to 4.2 amperes were transmitted through the grounded bipoles depending on the values of contact resistances encountered at various transmitting stations. At all times,

the magnetic sensor was placed at right angles to each receiver line during CSAMT data acquisition in Dikwa area.

The E-dipole separation was fixed at 200m, while the transmitter-receiver distance varied from 2 to 8km. Recordings were made beginning with the highest frequency number, 13 (F-high=8192 Hz) and reduced one step at a time after a time interval of 3 minutes to the lowest frequency number, -2 (F-low=0.25Hz). All data were automatically recorded and stored in the Turbo V4 receiver which had to go back to Maiduguri on daily basis at the end of each day's field work for data transfer.

RESULTS

The results of the CSAMT investigations in Dikwa area are presented in the form of a coloured Bostick section (apparent resistivity versus depth) fig. 5.

GEOELECTRICAL INTERPRETATIONS

Five CSAMT profiles (A, B, C, D and E) were sounded and processed to generate five Bostick sections. Each of the five Bostick sections revealed a pattern interpreted as three parallel faults (Zonge *et al*, 1986) similar to the ones on profile A presented in fig. 5, where the fault planes are indicated by three arrows. A complete interpretation of the five Bostick sections obtained on the profiles A, B, C, D, and E with a view to establishing the actual positions of the three parallel faults on each profile has been presented in figure 6. Figure 6 shows a set of three parallel faults oriented in a northeast-southwest direction.

These faults have the same orientation as the inferred lineaments observed on land satellite and shuttle images and confirmed with resistivity profiling by Isiorho and Nkereuwem (1996). This work has thus confirmed the well established trend of basement fracturing in northern Nigeria by previous workers (Daniel, 1999; Bassey *et al*, 2000; and Kamureyina, 2007 etc.)

CONCLUSION

The study has delineated three parallel deep-seated faults using the CSAMT technique in Dikwa area about 25km North of New Marte in the North western sector of lake Chad. Based on the Bostick section (Fig. 5), the faults are as deep as 10km. This fact tends to support the suggestion by Isiorho and Nkereuwem (1996) that the inferred lineament were indeed bedrock fractures. The work has equally established the fact that the inferred lineaments

detected by Isiorho and Nkereuwem (1996) and the parallel faults obtained in this study have the same NE-SW orientation towards Benue Trough.

We strictly believe that recharging the underlying Chad Formation aquifers through seepage and high rate of evaporation are not the only reasons for the disappearance of water from the Mega Lake Chad which ancient shoreline extended to Bama, a distance of over 130km from the present Lake. Only gigantic basement fractures acting as migratory routes have the capacity to drain such a colossal amount of water from Lake Chad.

Fig. 5. BOSTICK INV. APP. RESISTIVITY (Ex/Hy) (CORRECTED)
Resistivity in ohm-m

RECOMMENDATION

We wish to suggest that further remote sensing and geophysical works be carried out in areas between South of Dikwa and the Benue Trough to establish the continuity or otherwise of those basement fractures.

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